

CXL Memory Management for the CMS L1 Scouting System and Beyond

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ABSTRACT

The Level 1 (L1) Trigger at CMS performs fast reconstruction in FPGA logic, processing a subset of detector data at the 40 MHz bunch-crossing rate ("scouting"). This process selects the most interesting events for full read-out and processing in the software filter farm at a frequency of approximately 100 kHz. The emerging Compute Express Link (CXL) protocol operates over the PCIe physical layer and dynamically multiplexes IO, cache, and memory protocols. It is engineered to substantially reduce latency in heterogeneous and disaggregated computing through efficient resource sharing, shared memory pools, and enhanced data and operand movement between accelerators and target devices. In the context of ongoing collaboration efforts with Micron Technology, we aim to leverage CXL for the L1 Scouting ingestion and data processing chain, providing coherent and seamless access to buffered data from multiple processors and compute accelerators. Ultimately, the CXL-powered system will offer low-latency access to both raw and processed CMS data in a short-term staging area that precedes tape storage.

This project explores the feasibility and compatibility of integrating CXL into CMS's existing L1 Scouting system by working with demonstrator and test systems installed at CERN, assessing the protocol's potential to enhance the L1 Scouting process with efficient, cache-coherent data handling at scale, thereby contributing to the system's potential for CMS research. With the High Luminosity LHC upgrade and the expected increase in data volumes, the CMS Level-1 Scouting System requires advanced event selection and data processing techniques. And for this reason, this research investigates innovative solutions to address these needs, focusing on latency, bandwidth, and memory management challenges through the evaluation of CXL-enabled devices. By combining CXL's cache-coherency capabilities with the Fabric-attached memory file system (Famfs), the system can achieve disaggregated shared files and multi-host memory management. This ongoing integration within the SCDAQ software aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of these technologies in enhancing the performance and scalability of CMS's data processing framework.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) experiment at CERN's Large Hadron Collider (LHC) is tasked with analyzing the massive amount of data generated by particle collisions occurring at a rate of 40 million events per second (40 MHz). A challenge lies in the fact that it is not feasible to fully read out and process data from all detectors at this rate due to limitations in bandwidth and storage, which would require more than 480 Tb/s, but also for the physical characteristics of the detectors such as readout time or power consumption. To manage this, the Level 1 (L1) Trigger system is employed to quickly identify and select the most interesting events for further analysis, reducing the data rate from 40 MHz to approximately 100 kHz.

The CMS Level 1 Data Scouting (L1DS) is an advanced technique used within this framework to acquire and analyze data that would typically be discarded by the L1 Trigger. It involves the nonstandard use of the trigger for data acquisition, allowing researchers to access a broader range of physics by bypassing some of the constraints imposed by L1 latency and accept rate. This approach enables the CMS experiment to explore additional signatures and conduct more comprehensive analyses, thereby enriching its overall physics program [1].

As the LHC undergoes upgrades, particularly with the forthcoming High-Luminosity upgrade, the volume of data expected to be generated will significantly increase. This motivation presents new challenges in data acquisition, processing, and storage. Addressing these challenges will require the integration of emerging technologies, such as AI acceleration and real-time data indexing, into the existing data scouting infrastructure. These technologies will be crucial in maintaining and enhancing the CMS experiment's ability to process and analyze the ever-growing data volumes efficiently.

L1 DATA SCOUTING OVERVIEW

The L1DS system is designed to capture and process data at the full 40 MHz bunch crossing rate, focusing on a subset of the most valuable trigger primitives. The data acquisition process begins with FPGA boards that receive, align, and pre-process the data streams before transmitting them via high-speed Ethernet connections to a cluster of computing nodes. These nodes, running an Intel TBB-based data acquisition software (SCDAQ), perform further data reduction and online processing using the CMS reconstruction framework [2].

However, as data volumes continue to grow, the system faces significant challenges, particularly in managing high data throughput and maintaining low-latency processing. Efficient data handling and processing are essential to ensuring that the L1DS system can scale effectively to meet the demands of the High-Luminosity LHC, allowing CMS to continue its pursuit of physics analyses that might otherwise be constrained by traditional trigger limitations. **Figure 1** presents the current L1DS infrastructure main components and protocols.

Figure 1. Diagram of the CMS L1 Data scouting computing infrastructure currently in operation. Source: [3].

CXL MEMORY INTERFACES

The Compute Express Link (CXL) [4] protocol represents a transformative technology in the realm of heterogeneous and disaggregated computing. As a new alternate protocol capable of running over the standard PCIe physical layer, CXL dynamically multiplexes IO, cache, and memory protocols, enabling highly efficient resource sharing, shared memory pools, and enhanced data movement between accelerators and target devices. This protocol is specifically designed to significantly reduce latency, which is critical in high-performance computing environments such as the CMS L1 Scouting System. By integrating CXL into its online processing infrastructure, CMS aims to leverage these advanced capabilities to enhance the L1 scouting data processing pipeline. The ability to access data coherently and seamlessly from multiple processors and compute accelerators through CXL's shared memory architecture promises to improve processing efficiency and scalability, addressing the increasing data volumes expected from future LHC upgrades.

OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of the project is to integrate Micron CXL-enabled memory devices into the CMS L1DS system's ingestion and data processing chain. This integration aims to enhance the system by providing coherent and seamless access to buffered data across multiple processors and compute accelerators, significantly improving data handling efficiency. Additionally, the project seeks to achieve low-latency access to both raw and processed data within a short-term storage environment, thereby ensuring scalability and responsiveness in managing the increasing data volumes expected from the High-Luminosity LHC upgrades.

2. MEMORY LAKE CONCEPT

This proposal was designed to address the growing challenges in handling massive data volumes generated by systems like the CMS L1 Scouting System. As data volumes continue to increase, traditional memory architectures face limitations in terms of scalability, latency, and bandwidth. The Memory Lake architecture, shown in **Figure 2**, proposes a solution that leverages disaggregated memory resources, creating a shared memory pool that can be accessed by multiple hosts and accelerators. This architecture supports efficient, high-bandwidth, low-latency access to memory, enabling better data management and processing in environments that demand fast, large-scale data transfers. By utilizing shared memory across multiple systems, this architecture facilitates more efficient memory utilization, minimizes data duplication, and improves overall processing efficiency.

Figure 2. Diagram of the Memory Lake concept. Source: [3].

At the top, a pool of byte-addressable memory is accessible via CXL, enabling seamless access to shared memory across the entire system. Below the memory pool, CXL switches facilitate dynamic connectivity between various system components, including Ingestion Units (IUs), Processing Units (PUs), Accelerator Units (AUs), and Storage Units (SUs). The ingestion units receive high-speed data streams over 400 Gb/s optical links, which are processed by the processing and accelerator units before being stored in tiered storage, providing efficient data handling and improved processing capabilities. Combining the use of disaggregated shared files, using a fabric-attached file system, with cache-coherent CXL for byte-addressable memory would allow the creation of a memory lake with capacities in the order of hundreds of terabytes.

FAMFS FILE SYSTEM

The Fabric-Attached Memory File System (FAMFS) [5] is a key component in the Memory Lake architecture, providing the software infrastructure needed to manage disaggregated memory. FAMFS is a file system that allows shared memory to be accessed by multiple hosts, using memory mapping and DAX devices without the need for intermediate processor caching. This direct access capability ensures low-latency memory transactions, making it particularly well-suited for applications that require rapid memory access or the use of hardware accelerators, like GPUs or FPGAs.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

SERVER ENVIRONMENT

The experimental setup for the LD1S demonstrator of the integration with CXL technology is built on a hardware and software environment designed for high-performance data ingestion and processing. The server hardware comprises a Supermicro system equipped with two AMD EPYC 9454 CPUs, each offering 48 cores and capable of a peak bandwidth of 460 GB/s per socket, making it well-suited for handling large-scale data tasks. The system also includes two Micron CZ120 CXL Type 3 memory expansion modules, each with 256 GB DDR4 memory, supporting CXL.io and CXL.mem protocols, and delivering up to 36 GB/s of memory bandwidth with low latency. The operating system is based on a FAMFS-enabled Linux kernel (RHEL 9.3 with kernel 6.8-rc4), which facilitates efficient memory management and seamless integration of CXL memory devices within the data processing chain. **Figure 3** presents a photo of the server internals.

Figure 3. CXL host node at CMS USC. Server supplied by E4 Computer Engineering. Two CZ120 memory expansion modules provided by Micron. Source adapted from: [1].

i. MICRON MEMORY EXPANSION

The Micron CZ120 memory expansion module is a high-performance CXL Type 3 device designed to enhance memory capacity and bandwidth in advanced computing environments. Available in 128GB and 256GB configurations, the CZ120 leverages Micron's DDR4 technology, supporting data transfer speeds of up to 3200 MT/s. It operates over a PCIe Gen5 x8 interface, delivering a maximum bandwidth of up to 36 GB/s with a read latency as low as 90 nanoseconds under unloaded conditions. The module also features advanced RAS (Reliability, Availability, Serviceability) capabilities, including single error correction and double error detection (SECDDED) and single device data correction and error correction code (SDDC ECC) for error correction, thermal throttling, and secure boot features. The CZ120 is designed for seamless integration into high-density computing systems, providing a robust solution for applications requiring large, high-speed memory resources.

4. BENCHMARK RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section presents the benchmark results obtained from the experimental setup and carries out analysis of memory performance metrics such as latency, bandwidth, and throughput, as well as the comparison of results with expectations and previous benchmarks.

PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENTS

i. MEMORY LATENCY CHECKER

The Memory Latency Checker (MLC) [6] is a tool developed by Intel to measure and analyze memory latency and bandwidth in computing systems. It is particularly useful for evaluating the performance of memory subsystems, including those involving advanced technologies like CXL. MLC can perform both unloaded and loaded latency tests, providing insights into how memory latency changes under different bandwidth conditions. For example, it allows us to observe how higher bandwidth demands can lead to increased latency, which is crucial for optimizing system performance.

The tool supports various configurations, enabling detailed assessments of memory behavior in environments such as utilizing the Micron CZ120 memory expansion modules. In this context, MLC helps determine the efficiency of memory operations, ensuring that the system meets the stringent performance requirements for high-speed data processing. The measurements obtained results are shown in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Latency measured at different bandwidth points. These results were obtained using the Memory Latency Checker tool for one CZ120 memory module expansion device.

As **Figure 4** indicates, latency remains relatively low and stable across most bandwidth levels but begins to increase sharply as the system approaches its maximum bandwidth capacity, particularly around 25 to 35 GB/s. The steep rise in latency at higher bandwidths is most pronounced in the 0:1 and 1:1 read to non-temporal write ratios, which is typical as higher bandwidth demands lead to increased memory contention and reduced efficiency.

Conversely, mixed read-write workloads (represented by the pink and blue points) show more balanced performance, with lower latency at higher bandwidths compared to non-temporal write-dominant workloads. This demonstrates the importance of optimizing memory access patterns to maintain lower latency and achieve higher overall performance in systems utilizing the CZ120 memory module.

ii. STREAM

The STREAM [7] benchmark is a widely used synthetic benchmark designed to measure sustainable memory bandwidth (in MB/s) and the corresponding computation rate for simple vector operations. The benchmark consists of four primary functions, where each function tests different aspects of memory performance:

- **Copy:** Measures the rate of copying data from one location to another ($C = A$).
- **Scale:** Tests the rate of scaling a vector by a constant and storing the result ($B = \text{scalar} \times C$).
- **Add:** Measures the rate of adding two vectors and storing the result ($C = A + B$).
- **Triad:** Combines scaling and addition in a single operation ($A = B + \text{scalar} \times C$).

Figure 5 presents the results of the STREAM benchmark across four different configurations.

Figure 5. STREAM results for each memory device configuration.

In direct access (DAX) mode, the memory can be accessed directly without using the processor cache. The performance varies across functions, with the highest bandwidth observed in the Triad operation (22.67 GB/s) and the lowest in the Copy operation (15.34 GB/s). The average times are relatively consistent, though the Add operation has a slightly higher average time.

NUMA (Non-Uniform Memory Access) mode represents the performance when memory is accessed through a traditional DRAM configuration, where memory access time varies depending on the processor's proximity to the memory node. The bandwidth in NUMA mode is higher across all functions compared to DAX mode, with Triad and Add operations reaching approximately 23.97 GB/s. This mode also shows the lowest average times, reflecting an expected slightly better efficient memory access.

DAX Mode using SIMD (Single Instruction, Multiple Data) optimization is applied to improve parallel processing, allowing multiple data points to be processed with a single instruction. This mode shows an improvement over standard DAX mode, especially in the Copy operation, which reaches a bandwidth of 19.91 GB/s, a significant increase compared to the unoptimized DAX mode. The average times are slightly lower than standard DAX mode, indicating that SIMD optimization effectively improves performance, particularly in operations that can benefit from parallel processing.

DAX Mode using FAMFS files utilizes memory mapping system calls, which can improve performance on DAX devices by enabling more efficient data access. This configuration shows a balanced improvement across all functions, with the Copy function reaching 20.06 GB/s and Triad at 22.31 GB/s. The use of FAMFS files results in more consistent performance with lower variability in minimum and maximum times, which is particularly important in applications requiring predictable latency and throughput.

iii. MULTICHASE

The Multichase [8] benchmark tool operates by performing a series of pointer-chasing operations, which are highly sensitive to memory access latency. In this kind of operation, each memory access depends on the result of the previous access, creating a chain of dependent memory accesses. This pattern is common in various real-world applications, such as linked lists, trees, and other data structures that require non-sequential memory access. The results from **Table 1** provide insights into the relative performance of different memory access modes, helping to identify potential bottlenecks in memory access patterns.

(a) NUMA node distances				
node	0	1	2	3
0	10	32	50	60
1	32	10	60	50
2	255	255	10	255
3	255	255	255	10

(b) Multichase in NUMA mode				
node	0	1	2	3
0	111.3	206.5	176.4	330.0
1	-	-	328.7	180.3 ~ 224
2	-	-	-	-
3	-	-	-	-

(c) Multichase in DAX mode		
node	/dev/dax0.0	/dev/dax1.0
0	176.9	329.9
1	327.1	179.2

Table 1. Multichase results for NUMA and DAX modes.

The NUMA distances in the Table 1(a) represent the relative access cost between different nodes in the system. A lower value indicates closer proximity and, typically, lower latency, while higher values suggest greater distances and higher latencies.

The NUMA mode results in Table 1(b) reflect the performance when memory is accessed through a traditional NUMA configuration, where memory access times vary depending on the node-to-node distance. The latency and access efficiency are directly impacted by the NUMA topology, with closer nodes showing better performance due to lower memory access costs.

The DAX mode results in Table 1(c) would generally show very similar characteristics compared to NUMA mode, considering that the DAX devices dax0.0 and dax1.0 where online as nodes 2 and 3, respectively.

iv. STRESSAPPTST

StressAppTest [9] is a stress-testing tool designed to evaluate the stability and performance of memory and CPU subsystems under high load conditions. It simulates intensive workloads that involve continuous reading and writing to memory, which can help identify potential issues such as memory errors, thermal problems, or stability concerns in the memory or CPU. StressAppTest is particularly useful for ensuring that systems can handle heavy computational loads without failures or significant performance degradation. The tool is often used in environments where memory reliability and stability are critical, such as in servers or high-performance computing systems. **Figure 6** compares the performance of NUMA and DAX modes across different numbers of CPU cores.

Figure 6. StressAppTest results for CZ120 device, using multiple processing cores in NUMA and DAX modes.

Both NUMA and DAX modes show an initial rapid increase in bandwidth as the number of cores increases from 8 to 32 cores. This indicates that both memory configurations can effectively scale with the number of cores up to this point. After reaching around 40 cores, the bandwidth for both modes stabilize, with no significant increase as more cores are added. This suggests that the memory bandwidth reaches a saturation point where adding more cores does not contribute to higher throughput.

Both NUMA and DAX modes exhibit stable performance beyond 64 cores, with bandwidth remaining constant at around 20 GB/s. This indicates that both configurations can maintain consistent memory bandwidth under stress with a large number of cores, which is crucial for applications requiring high parallel processing capabilities.

5. DISCUSSIONS

The benchmark results from this project demonstrate the potential of CXL technology to enhance memory management and data processing in the CMS L1 Scouting system. The Memory Latency Checker tests revealed that CXL-enabled memory, such as the Micron CZ120 modules when mapped as DAX devices will provide competitive bandwidth compared to local DRAM per channel. The latency observed compares well with the traditional local DRAM devices, which were mapped as system-RAM in distant NUMA nodes. The STREAM benchmark highlighted the benefits of DAX mode, particularly when paired with optimizations like SIMD, showing better performance using improved concurrency access. The Multichase and StressAppTest benchmarks provided insights into the stability and scalability of CXL, demonstrating that it can maintain high bandwidth and consistent performance as the number of cores increases. These results confirm that CXL is capable of handling the high data throughput demands of CMS's L1 Scouting system.

The integration of CXL technology into the CMS L1 Scouting system appears to be both feasible and compatible with the current infrastructure. The CXL protocol's ability to operate over the PCIe physical layer allows it to fit within the existing hardware framework without requiring extensive modifications. Additionally, the use of CXL Type 3 devices, like the Micron CZ120 for memory expansion, aligns well with the current data processing model used by CMS. The benchmarks show that the system can handle the increased data volumes expected from the High-Luminosity LHC upgrades while maintaining the necessary latency and bandwidth performance. Moreover, the FAMFS file system facilitates seamless memory management across multiple hosts, further enhancing compatibility with the CMS L1 data processing chain.

Integrating CXL into the CMS L1 Scouting system has the potential to significantly improve the overall efficiency of the data acquisition and processing pipeline. The low-latency memory access enabled by CXL ensures that critical data can be processed faster, reducing the risk of bottlenecks during peak data influx periods. The disaggregated memory architecture, supported by byte-addressable shared memory pools, allows for more flexible resource allocation, enabling the system to scale more effectively as data volumes increase. Additionally, the ability to share memory across multiple processors and accelerators using CXL enhances parallel processing capabilities, making the scouting process more responsive to the complex demands of CMS data analysis. This should result in faster turnaround times for data processing and a higher overall throughput for critical physics events.

During the 2nd DARTS Hackathon at CERN (August 26 to 30, 2024), several key concepts were proposed and validated as essential steps for continuing this research, focusing on further optimization and integration of CXL into the CMS L1 Scouting system. This includes:

- **Expanding the use of FAMFS** to handle more complex data workflows, ensuring efficient memory management across multiple nodes and accelerators.
- **Virtualization of CXL resources**, including the emulation of persistent memory [10] and CXL switch fabrics [11, 12], which will be essential to simulate the full potential of CXL in a multi-tenant environment.

Finally, continued collaboration with industry partners like Micron will be key to ensuring that the latest advancements in CXL technology are integrated into the CMS data processing framework, preparing the system for future challenges.

In conclusion, CXL offers a robust and scalable solution for enhancing the CMS L1 Scouting system, providing a foundation for future upgrades and data processing advancements in high-energy physics.

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